

BSP control for visual pointing of satellite directional antennas for Geostationary Earth Orbit Service Operations

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Abstract—We present a novel approach for the visual driven pointing of satellite directional antennas based on a Belief Space Planning control (BSP). This work is part of a wider research program aiming at reducing the complexity and the cost of satellites dedicated to various tasks and to develop a system platform to manufacture them in orbit. BSP allows less accurate and cheaper antennas and satellite with respect to other control approaches. This will facilitate the 3D printing of their components and their assembly in orbit.

Index Terms—visual guided directional antennas, low accuracy space robots, soft space robots, Belief Space Planning

Fig. 1: Concept

I. INTRODUCTION

In this work we frame the problem of the pointing of a directional antenna on a geostationary orbit as a visual servoing problem and we propose a solution based on a Belief Space Planning (BSP) approach as we did in previous works [2]. This is a novel approach to the control of directional antennas in orbit as usually it is based on the explicit and detailed modelling of the satellite and utilizes model predictive control approaches, linear control or more sophisticated methods [5]. BSP has proven to be a very robust and reliable control approach for low-accuracy robots and where significant uncertainties are present [3, 4]. This allows to implement tasks by means of mechanically less sophisticated robots and less accurate sensors leading to significantly reduced costs. Our long term aim is to manufacture satellites in orbit and we believe that being able to use low accuracy (and compliant) satellites with less accurate sensors will make their manufacturing in orbit more feasible. An artistic rendering of the application framework can be found in Figure 1(a). The task of the satellite is depicted in Figure 1(b). The antenna needs to remain directed to the receiver on earth while the satellite follows its geostationary orbit.

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II. METHODOLOGY

We follow the methodology we already applied in [2] and elsewhere. There the approach proposed in [6] was adapted to the task of visual driven antenna pointing. Belief Space Planning pursues the concurrent reduction of uncertainty, measured by the covariance of the state estimates, and the reaching of the desired state. The ‘state’ is represented by a Gaussian Probabilistic Density Function, ‘belief’ about the unknown state of the system. The trajectory of the system, the antenna asset relative to the satellite in our case is approximated by a series of segments, obtained by Direct Transcription [1, 6].

At each step, identified by a segment, the controller receives the current reference point, which is utilized to move the antenna’s ‘belief state’ to the specified intermediate position. The procedure is iterated until the final desired state, identified by a Gaussian PDF is reached. The algorithm evaluates the adequacy of the calculated intermediate end point of the computed segment of the plan to approach the final position at each iteration. If the intermediate point is inadequate, the algorithm re-plans it.

In [6] a formal proof of the optimality of this approach under linear Gaussian process assumptions is provided. The observations $z_t \in Z$ of the distance between the goal and the antenna actual position are modeled as a non linear stochastic function of the vector $x_t \in X$, representing the state of the antenna and of the environment, as in (1).

$$z_t = g(x_t) + \xi \quad (1)$$

where g is a deterministic function of the measurement and ξ is a zero mean Gaussian noise with covariance W_t , dependent on the state. The deterministic function f links the new state to the older one under the control action u_t

$$x_{t+1} = f(x_t, u_t) \quad (2)$$

where f and g are differentiable functions of x_t and u_t . The controller knows the state through a probabilistic density function $P(x)$. The parameters of the distribution are the “belief state” $b_t = [m_t^T \ s_t^T]^T$, where m_t is the mean of the belief state and $s = [s_1^T, \dots, s_d^T]^T$ is a vector composed by the d columns of the covariance matrix Σ . In the hypotheses of linear Gaussian dynamics, the belief state can be updated as below:

$$x_{t+1} = A_t(x_t - m_t) + f(m_t, u_t) \quad (3a)$$

$$z_t = C_t(x_t - m_t) + g(f(m_t, u_t)) + \xi \quad (3b)$$

where A_t and C_t are the Jacobian matrices $A_t = \frac{\delta f}{\delta x}(m_t, u_t)$, $C_t = \frac{\delta g}{\delta x}(m_t)$. The Gaussian distribution is then:

$$\Sigma_t : P(x) = \mathcal{N}(x/m_t, \Sigma_t) \quad (4)$$

Under these assumptions, by adding the assumption of maximum likelihood of the observations, it can be proved that a series of segments with an associated set of control actions b minimizing the cost function J can be derived by iteration.

$$J(b_{\tau:T}, u_{\tau:T}) = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i (\hat{n}_i^T \Sigma_i \hat{n}_i)^2 + \sum_{t=\tau}^{T-1} \tilde{m}_t^T Q \tilde{m}_t + \tilde{u}_t^T R \tilde{u}_t \quad (5)$$

where $b_{\tau:T}$ is the subset of the state space, $u_{\tau:T}$ are the corresponding actions for a given state space trajectory, Q and R are weight matrices, and the n_i are the versors of the belief space along which the optimization is performed. Finally, Σ_T is the covariance matrix at the end of the segment, and m_t^T the value of the mean of the Gaussian of the measures. The minimum of the function J is obtained by a standard SQP (Sequential Quadratic Programming) algorithm. A linear quadratic regulator is applied to move the state inside each segment. The procedure is shortly described in Algorithm 1.

Using a LQR standard control makes BSP planning more efficient: optimizing the control actions for the system helps stabilizing the belief space trajectory despite the nonlinear dynamics of the system.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Our experiments have been conducted in simulation in Matlab on a standard Windows laptop PC. In Figure 2(a), we see the norm of the distance of the projection of the ideal focus point of the antenna from the target point on earth surface. Figure 2(b) shows that the angle of the antenna with reference to an ideal arbitrary fixed reference with center coincidental with the center of the earth move correctly over time.

Algorithm 1: BSP Algorithm

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1 Input:  $b_0, b_{goal}$  Output:  $u_{1:s}$ 
2 initBSP();
3 for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
4    $(\tilde{m}_{1:s}, \tilde{u}_{1:s}) = \text{CreatePlan}(m_0, m_{goal});$ 
5   for  $j = 1$  to  $s - k$  do
6      $k = r + j;$ 
7      $u_t = \text{LQR}(\tilde{u}_t, \tilde{m}_t, m_t);$ 
8      $z_t = g(x_t) + \xi;$ 
9      $m_{t+1} = \text{EKF}(m_t, u_t, z_t);$ 
10    if  $\|\tilde{m}_t - m_t\| < thr_1$  then
11      while  $e_t > thr_2$  do
12         $\eta_t = \text{DriveVehicle}(m_t);$ 
13    else
14       $r = r + j - 1;$ 

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Fig. 2: Results

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We developed a system that allows the visual driven pointing of a directional antenna on a satellite in a Geostationary orbit. Our simulation runs show the viability of the approach.

We plan to perform mixed reality simulations in order to improve the design of the system. Then we will conduct experiments underwater in a pool, and then if successful in orbit.

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